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Cultivar	IRRI accession number	Origin	Damage rating ^a (grade 0-9)	
			<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
<i>Moderately resistant to N. nigropictus and N. virescens</i>				
Gauk	33072	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
Chini Atap	37403	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
BR3	38625	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
Dharia Bogi	43814	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
Hanpa (Black)	43851	Bangladesh	5.0	4.0
Maguria	43921	Bangladesh	5.0	5.0
Sxc 108	35172	India	4.3	4.3
Amla	44932	India	5.0	5.7
I.B. Rose/Latisail	45848	India	5.0	5.0
Karpursail	46050	India	5.0	5.0
Rupsail	46586	India	5.0	5.0
Sachi	46612	India	5.0	5.0
Sadlaghu	46625	India	5.0	5.0
Intan	4230	Indonesia	5.0	5.0
Mas	5334	Indonesia	5.0	5.0
Dikwee	7814	Nigeria	4.3	5.0
<i>Resistant to N. virescens and susceptible to N. nigropictus</i>				
Chungur bali	25855	Bangladesh	6.3	3.0
Muijuri	25907	Bangladesh	7.0	1.7
Sona Biron	31633	Bangladesh	9.0	1.7
Lal Aswina	31670	Bangladesh	9.0	1.7
Molladiga	31675	Bangladesh	9.0	3.7
Kala Aman 961	32908	Bangladesh	7.0	3.7
Ellai	37424	Bangladesh	7.0	3.0
Lal paika	37523	Bangladesh	7.0	3.0
Laki 146	37709	Bangladesh	7.0	1.7
Dudhswar 15-146	37956	Bangladesh	7.0	1.7
Jessobalam 3-23	38009	Bangladesh	7.0	3.7
Latisail 11-122	38082	Bangladesh	9.0	3.0
Dhalgora	43813	Bangladesh	6.3	3.0
Ta-Poo-Cho z	4285	China	7.0	3.0
Ptb 20	5920	India	7.0	3.7
Katki	46091	India	7.0	3.0
Ratrio	28181	Pakistan	7.0	3.0
Milagrosa Mutant	26967	Philippines	7.0	3.7
IR5853-135-3-P3	39425	Philippines	7.0	3.0
IR5865-32-3	39434	Philippines	7.0	3.7
IR5896-10-2	39441	Philippines	7.0	3.0
<i>Resistant to N. nigropictus and susceptible to N. virescens</i>				
Najirsail	37237	Bangladesh	9.0	3.0
Peta	35	India	7.0	3.7
CO13	4897	India	9.0	3.7
ARC12176	41016	India	7.0	3.0
ARC14664	41672	India	7.0	3.0
Jessoa	45893	India	7.0	3.0
Katalgaria	46075	India	7.0	3.0
Bir-Co-Se-Mau 7	4349	China	6.3	3.7
IR2003-P7-7-4-2	32671	Philippines	9.0	3.7
IR2031-238-5-2-6-2	32680	Philippines	7.0	3.0
IR2070-464-1-3-6	32701	Philippines	9.0	3.7
IR42	36959	Philippines	7.0	3.7
Kosattawee	8927	Sri Lanka	6.3	3.7
Sir	Muragan36279	Sri Lanka	9.0	3.0

^a 0 = highly resistant, 9 = susceptible.

were resistant (grades 1-3), 99 (48.5%) moderately resistant (grades 3.1-5), and 54 (26.5%) susceptible to *N. nigropictus* (scores 5.1-7); and 96 (47.1%) resistant, 38 (18.6%) moderately resistant, and 70 (34.3%) susceptible to *N. virescens* (see table). Twenty-nine cultivars were resistant to both species, 21 were resistant to *N. virescens* but susceptible to *N. nigropictus*, and 14 were resistant to *N. nigropictus* but susceptible to *N. virescens*. Accessions resistant to both leafhopper species should be considered for use as donors in the breeding program for GLH resistance. □

Screening for resistance of IR varieties to green leafhoppers (GLH)

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Several rices have been identified and incorporated in breeding programs in Asia for *Nephotettix virescens* resistance. Twenty-seven modern (IR5-IR62) rices with moderate to high levels of *N. virescens* resistance have been released.

We evaluated IRRI varieties IR5 to IR60 for resistance to *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus*, another common rice green leafhopper, in a seedbox screening test. Separate seedboxes were used for each hopper species. Seeds were sown in rows in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with Nira as the susceptible check. At 7 d after sowing seedlings were thinned to 15-20, entry and each was infested with 4-5 3d-instar nymphs of *N. nigropictus* or *N. virescens*. When the susceptible check died, test entries were rated for damage by the 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) 0-9 scale. Treatments were arranged in a complete randomized design with three replications.

Although the IR varieties were not bred for *N. nigropictus* resistance, levels of resistance were generally higher than

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Reactions of IR varieties to *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens* in the seedbox screening test, IIRRI, 1983-84.

Variety	Damage rating ^a			
	<i>N. nigropictus</i>		<i>N. virescens</i>	
IR5	6.3	de	7.0	def
IR8	5.7	cde	6.3	cde
IR20	6.3	de	7.0	def
IR22	5.0	bcde	8.3	ef
IR24	4.3	bcd	4.3	abc
IR26	3.7	bc	5.7	bcd
IR28	3.0	b	3.7	ab
IR29	3.0	b	3.0	a
IR30	3.7	bc	3.0	a
IR32	4.3	bcd	6.3	cde
IR34	4.3	bcd	4.3	abc
IR36	3.0	b	6.3	cde
IR38	4.3	bcd	5.7	bcd
IR40	5.0	bcde	5.7	bcd
IR42	4.3	bcd	7.0	def
IR43	3.7	bc	4.3	abc
IR44	4.3	bcd	4.3	abc
IR45	4.3	bcd	5.7	bcd
IR46	5.7	cde	6.3	cde
IR48	5.0	bcde	7.0	def
IR50	4.3	bcd	3.7	ab
IR52	4.3	bcd	3.7	ab
IR54	4.3	bcd	3.7	ab
IR56	3.0	b	3.0	a
IR58	3.0	b	3.7	ab
IR60	3.0	b	3.0	a
Nira (susceptible check)	9.0	e	9.0	f

^a Av of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. The damage rating is based on the 1980 SES 0-9 scale.

those to *N. virescens*. Twelve varieties had similar reactions to both species (see table). IR56, IR58, and IR60 are highly resistant to both *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens*. They also have resistance to brown planthopper. □

Screening wild rices for resistance to green leafhopper (GLH)

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We screened 91 wild rices for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Stål) and *N. virescens* (Distant) using the seedbox test in the greenhouse. Separate seedboxes were used for each GLH species. Test entries were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with resistant IR29 and susceptible Nira. Each seedbox was a

Reaction of wild rices to *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens* in the seedbox screening test, IIRRI, 1983-84.

Species	Origin	IRRI acc. no.	Damage rating ^a	
			<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Costa Rica	100168	1.0	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	100172	1.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Japan	100179	1.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaya	100180	1.7	2.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Burma	100181	1.0	1.7
<i>O. sativa/O. rufipogon</i>	India	100183	2.0	4.3
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	Taiwan, China	100820	0.7	0.7
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	Taiwan, China	100821	3.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	100883	1.0	1.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	100885	1.0	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	India	100887	1.0	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	100890	1.7	0.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	100891	1.7	1.7
<i>O. punctata</i>	India	100892	5.7	1.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	USA	100895	1.7	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Thailand	100896	1.0	1.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Mexico	100914	1.0	0.7
<i>O. sativa/O. nivara</i>	Cambodia	100917	1.7	3.7
<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	100937	1.0	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	100947	3.0	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	100948	1.0	2.3
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	100953	1.0	2.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	100956	1.0	0.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Mexico	100959	3.7	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	100962	3.7	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	100963	1.0	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	100964	3.7	0.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Costa Rica	100965	5.0	0.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Panama	100966	1.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	100973	3.7	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101073	3.7	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101074	3.0	2.3
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101077	5.7	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101078	5.0	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101081	4.3	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101082	5.0	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101084	5.7	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101086	5.0	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101089	5.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101094	6.3	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101096	3.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101097	0.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101099	3.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101100	3.7	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101101	3.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101112	3.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101113	5.7	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101114	4.3	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101115	1.3	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101117	6.3	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101118	5.7	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101121	7.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101122	3.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101123	4.3	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101124	3.0	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101125	5.7	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101126	4.3	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101128	5.3	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101129	5.7	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101132	3.0	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101133	5.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101137	3.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101139	3.0	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101141	3.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101142	5.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101143	1.3	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	101149	3.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	101150	1.3	0.7